

1 **Activation of Xist by mutation of a DNA repair helicase, ERCC3, implicates DNA excision repair in**
2 **transcriptional modulation of Xist associated with DNA damage.**

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7 Xist is activated by tumor suppressor loss or mutation. We discovered and described Xist activation and
8 repression by genetic depletion of 53bp1, Rif1, BRCA1 and MRE11A together suggesting an intrinsic
9 relationship between homologous recombination (HR) or non homologous end joining (NHEJ)-type repair
10 of DNA damage and Xist modulation in cells separate from its function in development during Barr body
11 establishment. We describe here modulation of Xist non-coding RNA by mutation of the genes
12 corresponding to the xeroderma pigmentosum B complementation group (XPB), ERCC3.

13 Non-developmentally oriented Xist activation and repression resulting from tumor suppressor impairment
14 likely corresponds to the same event as Xist modulation resulting from perturbation of HR/NHEJ double
15 strand break repair; this also likely includes the nucleotide excision repair pathway.

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1. Kim, Jinseok et al. "Lesion recognition by XPC, TFIIH and XPA in DNA excision repair." Nature
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